

The value of particle physics research at CERN as public good

Purchase number CA9283916 Deliverable n. 5 FCC-200220231503_CINT_final report_V0100

Digital Object Identifier: 10.5281/zenodo.7766949

V0.1, 20 February 2023 authored by L. Secci (Eumetra)

V0.2, 28 February 2023 reviewed by J. Gutleber (CERN)

V0.3, 21 March 2023 reviewed by E. Sirtori (CSIL)

V1.0, 24 March 2023, reviewed and approved by J. Gutleber (CERN)

Main Author: Luca Secci (EUMETRA)
E-Mail: luca.secci@eumetra.com
Contributions from Erica Delugas and Francesco Giffoni (CSIL)

Disclaimer: The Future Circular Collider Innovation Study (FCCIS) receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant No 951754. The findings, interpretations and conclusions presented in this document are entirely those of the author(s) and should not be attributed in any manner to CERN or other institutions. Any errors remain those of the author(s).

We are very grateful to Johannes Gutleber for his advice and collaboration.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

TABLE OF CONTENTS	1
LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS	2
INTRODUCTION AND MAIN FINDINGS	3
1. METHODOLOGY	5
1.1 THE CONTINGENT VALUATION APPROACH	5
1.2 DESIGN OF THE QUESTIONNAIRE	6
1.3 SAMPLING STRATEGY AND ADMINISTRATION	8
1.3.1 Preliminary desk research	8
1.3.2 Survey set-up	9
1.3.3 Pilot test	9
1.3.4 Large scale survey	10
1.3.5 Quality assurance and monitoring.....	10
2. ATTITUDES TOWARDS SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH	11
3. AWARENESS ABOUT CERN.....	13
4. WILLINGNESS TO FINANCIALLY PARTICIPATE (WTP).....	17
4.1 THE ELICITATION PROCEDURE	17
4.2 RESULTS	21
REFERENCES	28
ANNEX I - BIDDING SCHEME IN CHF.....	29
ANNEX II - CONSENT FORM (ENGLISH VERSION)	30
ANNEX III - THE QUESTIONNAIRE (UK VERSION)	31
THE VALUE OF PARTICLE PHYSICS RESEARCH AT CERN AS PUBLIC GOOD	31
A SURVEY AMONG TAXPAYERS IN GERMANY, ITALY, POLAND, US, ISRAEL, JAPAN, AND UK	31
THE CONTINGENT VALUATION QUESTIONNAIRE (V06 09.08.2022)	31
<i>Bidding Scheme</i>	31
SECTION B: YOUR KNOWLEDGE OF CERN	34
ANNEX IV - SAMPLE DEMOGRAPHICS VS COUNTRY POPULATION	41
ANNEX V - DETAILS ABOUT CERN AWARENESS.....	49
ANNEX VI - WTP DISTRIBUTIONS	53

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

CAPI	Computer Aided Personal Interviews
CAWI	Computer Aided Web Interviews
CEA	French Alternative Energies and Atomic Energy Commission
CERN	European Organization for Nuclear Research
CINT	CINT Uk Ltd, London Uk
CSIL	CSIL Scrl , Milan, IT
CNRS	French National Centre for Scientific Research
CV	Contingent Valuation
EUMETRA	Eumetra International SA, Lugano CH
ESA	European Space Agency
ESRF	European Synchrotron Radiation Facility
IMF	International Monetary Fund
INSEE	Institut national de la statistique et des études économiques (National Institute of Statistics and Economic Studies - France)
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organization
NASA	National Aeronautics and Space Administration
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
NOAA	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration, US Department of Commerce
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization
WHO	World Health Organisation

INTRODUCTION AND MAIN FINDINGS

In the framework of the Future Circular Collider Innovation Study (FCCIS), in 2022 CERN issued a call to perform a large-scale survey in seven countries to a representative sample of the adult population in each country. This document is the summary report of the project under purchase number CA9283916, related to the international survey “The value of particle physics research as public good”. The project had the following main objectives:

- **Assess the public’s awareness of CERN** and its research activity in countries with different types of relationship with CERN, including CERN member and non-member states that correspond to a scenario of potential FCC contributors;
- **Assess if and how much a Future Circular Collider (FCC) research programme is worth to a layperson** unfamiliar with fundamental scientific research activities. The value is monetised through the concept of "Willingness To financially Participate" (WTP) in such a scientific research activity;
- **Test whether the individual WTP is influenced by the information about the equivalent per-capita annual contribution destined to CERN by its member states**, which are considered to be potential contributors to an FCC research programme. This annual contribution was calculated by dividing the total public contribution paid by member states (covered indirectly by taxes) by the number of adult citizens in those states. Specifically understand:
 - If the WTP is greater than the annual per-capita public contribution then the validity of the per-capita public contribution is confirmed;
 - If the WTP is smaller actual annual per-capita public contribution then there is a discrepancy between the value perceived and the value paid.

This study is built on previous successful experiments conducted in France in 2017 and in Switzerland in 2019 and enlarged the scope to seven additional countries. Five surveyed countries are CERN member states and two are not members of CERN, but are involved in the LHC research programme and in the FCC international feasibility study collaboration. The fieldwork took place from September to November 2022 and involved 8'443 respondents. In total, with the respondents in France and in Switzerland, 10'448 respondents are considered in the analysis.

This document explains the methodology applied, including a detailed description of all the fieldwork phases (section 1), reports the descriptive statistics of respondents and their awareness of CERN scientific research and its mission (Section 3 and 4), and introduces the WTP results (Section 4).

The main findings of the report are:

- **The awareness of CERN is far below that of several other international organisations** such as NASA, WHO and UNESCO, but it is higher than that of IMF, FAO and ESA. In general, **less than half of respondents (41%) are aware of what CERN and its mission are**. This awareness varies from country to country: the percentage is higher in CERN member states, ranging from 30% in Israel to 64% in Italy, up to 80% in Switzerland. In contrast, only 27% of respondents in the USA and 13% in Japan had heard about CERN before the survey.
- **The share of respondents with a positive WTP ranges from 29% in Japan, to over 70% in the UK, Poland, Italy, Switzerland and the USA**. The specific WTP value varies considerably from country to country, with median values ranging from CHF 20 per person per year in Switzerland to CHF 2 in France (both are CERN member states). For non-member states, the median WTP varies between CHF 24 in the USA and zero in Japan¹. However, the mean value is CHF 10 for Japan which means that a significant fraction of the Japanese

¹ These values are calculated on the entire sample of respondents, including those with WTP=0. For additional figures of WTP for the share of respondents with a positive WTP, see Table 1 below and Section 4.2.

adult population values that type of scientific research. The **variability is explained by the socioeconomic characteristics** of respondents in each country, including the **level of awareness, opinions about CERN, and attitudes towards scientific research in general.**

- Considering only CERN member states that contribute to the CERN annual budget, results indicate that **the WTP is larger than the current actual tax-based contribution per capita in each individual member state.** That finding holds true even adopting the median WTP which is a more conservative measure than the mean of the WTP distribution (Annex VI). Table 1 summarises the results.
- The report shows that **the value of a scientific research programme based on a Future Circular Collider perceived by respondents is higher than the actual tax amount transferred to CERN by the respective countries, and therefore no discrepancies exist between the WTP and the contributions actually paid today and potentially being paid by future additional contributing states.**

Table 1. WTP survey results overview

Country	Respondents aware of CERN	Respondents with WTP > 0	WTP per person (all responders)		WTP per person (only respondents with WTP>0)		Average tax contribution per person in 2021	Total N of Respondents	Year of the survey
			Mean	Median	Mean	Median			
	%	%	CHF	CHF	CHF	CHF	CHF	N	Y
CERN member states									
Switzerland	80	73	55	20	67	50	6	1'000	2019
UK	44	77	30	14	39	19	4	1'053	2022
Italy	65	76	29	13	38	22	2	1'084	2022
Germany	39	69	20	11	29	22	3	1'027	2022
Israel	28	68	16	6	23	15	3	1'094	2022
France	46	52	4 to 14	2	28	11	3	1'005	2018
Poland	38	77	9	6	12	10	1	1'072	2022
Non-member states									
USA	27	73	44	24	61	48	zero	2'048	2022
Japan	13	29	10	0	35	18	zero	1'065	2022

Source: Authors.

1. METHODOLOGY

1.1 The Contingent Valuation Approach

The methodology applied to achieve the intended objectives is the Contingent Valuation (CV) approach. This is a stated preference (survey) method in which respondents are asked to state their preferences in hypothetical, contingent or future markets/scenarios, allowing them to elicit demands for goods or services that are currently not traded in markets. **In our case, the contingent scenario is the construction of the FCC, while the public preferences are monetised through the concept of willingness to financially participate (WTP).** The survey draws on a representative compiled sample of individuals in each individually surveyed country (see below) who are asked to imagine that the FCC will be built, and that they can financially contribute to it. The sample of respondents is randomly selected among the target population according to a selection of observable socioeconomic characteristics such as gender, age, income, education, and other demographics to reflect the entire population's main features in that country. This permits to estimate the aggregate WTP for the FCC investment scenario at the country level starting from the interviewed sample. The CV approach is a well-established methodology². It has been widely used for estimating the public WTP of environmental, health, cultural³ and big science projects, including FCC in earlier surveys in France in 2018 and in Switzerland in 2019⁴.

The CV approach suffers, however, from the reliance on a hypothetical scenario, which may lead people to overestimate the true value of their WTP. A percentage of respondents may declare higher WTP values compared to the value they would actually pay in the real scenario, where they are asked for real money. This effect is known as the “hypothetical bias”. To mitigate this bias risk and to induce respondents to reveal their true WTP, several complementary strategies were adopted in this study, including social responsibility techniques, the signature of a declaration of honour, policy consequentiality and informing the participants about what they already actually pay to CERN as taxpayers in the form of annual income tax contributions.⁵ The analysis excludes enthusiastic respondents with high WTP answers that are considered outliers (Box 1).

BOX 1. Social psychological techniques to mitigate the hypothetical bias risk of the CV method

In the present analysis, the following methods were employed to mitigate the hypothetical bias [5; 12; 13] (See the consent form in Annex II):

- Respondents were informed that the survey was on a voluntary basis, and that it was designed in compliance with privacy laws in force in their own countries.
- The implementation of social responsibility techniques conveying respondents the idea that their role, while answering the questions, is important because they are also acting on behalf of non-sampled people, and are therefore invited to provide honest and sincere answers.
- Policy consequentiality techniques make respondents aware that the survey results will actually influence the decision-making process about future investments at CERN.
- The respondents were asked to sign a declaration of honour concerning the honesty and correctness of the information they provided.

To further increase the possibility of eliciting valid preferences, much effort was put into the design of the questionnaire with the objective of ensuring that respondents from all educational levels, ages, and different life experiences would be able to comprehend the language, concepts,

² OECD (2018), "Contingent valuation method", in *Cost-Benefit Analysis and the Environment: Further Developments and Policy Use*, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/9789264085169-7-en>.

³ For examples of CV applications see references [1; 2; 8; 10; 11; 16; 17]

⁴ See [6; 7; 9]

⁵ To be valid, a contingent valuation (CV) study as the present one must follow strict implementation rules. The NOAA Panel in 1993 [3] and, more recently, the 2017 '*Contemporary Guidance for Stated Preference Studies*' [14] laid down the rules to correctly carry out a CV study.

and questions used in the survey. To this end, CINT, Eumetra International, CSIL⁶, CERN and a group of external economic scientists with experience in the field acting as advisors working on non-related research programs were involved in meeting the requirements of clarity and understandability of the questionnaire for the public through various iterations. Moreover, the questionnaire was only launched after extensive pre-testing, while a two-page document with photos and a two-minute movie on what CERN is and what its particle physics research consists of were designed and distributed in the different local languages of the target countries.

1.2 Design of the questionnaire

Following the work carried out for France in 2018 and Switzerland in 2019, in 2022 seven additional countries were included in the study: five CERN Member States contributing to the CERN budget with annual in-cash membership fees, and two non-CERN Member States. The latter do not contribute directly to the CERN budget in-cash, but they do regularly contribute to the scientific experiments and collaborations with in-kind contributions in terms of personnel and scientific equipment.⁷ Table 2 reports the seven countries covered in 2022, along with the contribution to the CERN budget.⁸

Table 2. Countries included in the current and previous surveys

Country	Country status	Contribution to the 2021 CERN budget in CHF	% of the total 2021 CERN budget
France	Member state	162'651'400	13.91 %
Germany	Member state	243'978'500	20.87 %
Israel	Member state	22'390'950	1.91 %
Italy	Member state	122'471'350	10.48 %
Poland	Member state	33'135'900	2.83 %
Switzerland	Member state	45'973'250	3.96 %
UK	Member state	173'742'400	14.86 %
USA	Observer	zero	n/a
Japan	Observer	zero	n/a

Sources: Authors' elaboration on the 2021 CERN budget⁹.

⁶ CSIL srl is responsible for the socioeconomic impact WP of the FCCIS study. CSIL conducted the experiments in France and in Switzerland.

⁷ The USA's annual contribution in-kind (i.e., materials) is about 29 MCHF, while Japan contributes 4 MCHF (Report on the CERN Non-Member State contributions 2021/2022. 210th Session of the CERN Council, 16 December 2022).

⁸ The CERN has 23 member states: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Czech Republic, Denmark, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Israel, Italy, Netherlands, Norway, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom. The total annual contributions by CERN member states in 2021 was CHF 1,168,922,250. [chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://cds.cern.ch/record/2747877/files/English.pdf](https://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcglclefindmkaj/https://cds.cern.ch/record/2747877/files/English.pdf)

⁹ Final Budget of the Organization for the sixty-seventh financial year, <https://cds.cern.ch/record/2747877/files/English.pdf>

The questionnaire was the result of numerous rounds of consultations, both formal and informal ones, involving several stakeholders and experts inside and outside CERN (see [6] for details). To assure that the results of this survey could be integrated with the results of the surveys done in the two hosting countries France and Switzerland, the same questionnaire was used, with the following minor amendments:

- The language of the questionnaire was tailored to the country in which the survey was administered: English for UK and USA, German for Germany, Japanese for Japan, Italian for Italy, Hebrew for Israel, and Polish for Poland.
- The questionnaire was designed in compliance with the different national laws on respondents' privacy, anonymity and treatment of data, the GDPR¹⁰ for European countries, and the CERN's Operational Circular n° 11 (OC11) on the processing of personal data. Respondents participated voluntarily by signing an informed consent form that notified them, among other things, of the electronic storage of the answers with limited access to the research Team and the use of anonymised data only for scientific purposes (Annex I).
- Question A.4, asking about the awareness of CERN as compared to other organisations, was enriched with additional international and national organisations to cover the additional countries.
- The list of options in questions C.4 and C.6, asking the reasons for either being or not being willing to financially participate, were extended to be able to make a finer grained analysis (see below);
- To better profile the respondents with respect to their educational background, a question about the specific field of education was added in Section D.

The questionnaire was organised into four sections (Annex 2):

- SECTION A '*YOUR INTERESTS*' investigates interviewees' general interests and opinions about the importance of scientific research.
- Section B '*YOUR KNOWLEDGE OF CERN*' focuses on CERN and its research activity. A two-page description of CERN and a two-minute video visualising what particle physics research at CERN consists of were provided to interviewees. Some questions about the awareness and opinion of CERN were asked before the provision of this information material, and some were asked after reading the information material and watching the video. This allowed for making before/after comparisons and collecting real (i.e., not biased) people's perceptions about CERN.
- SECTION C '*YOUR SUPPORT OF CERN*' contains specific questions aiming at eliciting respondents' willingness to financially participate (WTP) in particle physics research. All WTP-related questions were asked after the provision of the information material. In this way, respondents were given a common information set to support their decision to contribute financially.
- SECTION D '*YOUR PROFILE*' includes questions on the respondents' demographic and socioeconomic characteristics. This study inquired about gender, age, level of education, field of education, occupational status, income, family size, region and zone (urban-periphery or rural) of residence.

¹⁰ The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) entered into force in 2016 after passing European Parliament, and as of May 25, 2018, all organizations were required to be compliant. Regulation (EU) 2016/679 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A02016R0679-20160504&qid=1532348683434>

1.3 Sampling strategy and administration

The fieldwork, including the sampling strategy and the administration of the questionnaire, consisted of several phases reported in Table 3. They are described one by one in what follows, while additional details are reported in the individual progress reports of the study.

Table 3. Fieldwork phases

Phase	Description
Preliminary desk research	Research from official statistics to identify the target population, the sample size, and the interview modality.
Survey set-up	It includes the design of the questionnaire and the interview programme .
Pilot tests	Testing of the interview programme on a small scale in real circumstances before the main fieldwork.
Launch on large scale	Main fieldwork.
Monitoring and quality check	Verification of the validity of the answers collected.

Sources: Authors.

1.3.1 Preliminary desk research

Preliminary desk research was conducted to inform the following decisions:

- Identification of the target population of the survey;
- Identification of the size of the sample to be interviewed in each country;
- Identification of the most suitable interview modality (e.g., face-to-face, CAWI, CAPI¹¹).

The identification of the target population started from the fact that CERN is funded through member states' contributions, which ultimately come from taxpayers' contributions. Therefore, to give an indication of the people awareness of CERN and the public WTP, the reference universe for this survey is the share of adult population that in principle is considered being able to make their own spending decisions. It refers to **the adult population aged from 18 to 75 years**.¹²

Based on the target population, **the choice of the sample size to be surveyed was 1'000 adult individuals in each CERN member state and Japan, and 2'000 adult individuals in the USA** because of the larger population. Three criteria guided this choice:

- 1) **Ensure a small statistical error to achieve a confidence level of more than 95%**. While the sample of 1'000 units is a benchmark for public polls, including electoral surveys, marketing surveys typically use a smaller sample. The larger sample sizes employed in this study ensure a confidence interval with a more than 95% confidence level. Specifically, by repeating the survey in different samples of the same size, 95 out of 100 times the estimates (e.g., the mean WTP or the share of people aware of CERN) will fall between the range of +/- 3,10% in the case of the sample size of 1'000 individuals and +/- 2,19% in the case of 2'000¹³.
- 2) **The need to reflect the demographic traits of the population relevant to this study**. The sampling strategy was performed to be representative of the population according to five key parameters: **gender, age, level of education, income, and geographical area of residence**. Official statistical sources such as Eurostat for the European countries, and

¹¹ CAWI (Computer Assisted Web Interviewing) refers to survey via the web, while CATI (Computer Assisted Telephone Interview) refers to the development of interviews via telephone.

¹² Persons above 75 years are often excluded from surveys because are difficult to reach and not willing to participate. On top of that, this group of people is not recommended to provide indication on investments very far into the future because cannot be interested in, and therefore, they could provide misleading answers.

¹³ To note that the statistical error becomes independent of the country's population above some threshold of the sample size, e.g., 1,000 units. The latter is used to represent the infinite universe, that is why the same sample size of 1,000 respondents was used, e.g., for Poland with about 10 million inhabitants and Italy with about 60 million. To be on the safe side, we use a sample of 2,000 respondents for the USA (330 million inhabitants), but this only marginally reduced the statistical error.

national statistical offices for the USA, Japan and Israel were used to profile the population in line with these variables. Interviews were continuously monitored to reflect the composition of the entire population and avoid misrepresentation towards specific groups of people with potential negative consequences on the validity of our results (e.g., having an over-representation of more educated, richer people or under-representation of people living in less urbanised areas). Annex IV reports a set of tables which compare the sample of interviewees with the reference population for each country and key socioeconomic traits. No relevant differences exist, which demonstrates the reliability of the findings of this research.

- 3) **Cost-efficiency.** Face-to-face interviews are costly and the budget allocated to research projects are limited. Increasing the size of the samples would not have led to a significant reduction in the statistical error. Therefore, the sample sizes chosen are a good compromise from the cost-efficiency perspective.

The preliminary desk research phase was also performed to support **the choice of the CAWI modality to conduct the interviews**. In 2021, the percentage of households with a web access was more than 90% in all the countries surveyed and specifically 90% in Italy, USA, and Israel, 92% in Germany and Poland, 93% in Japan, and 98% in the UK (progress reports contain further insights). Such higher percentages along with its convenience from the cost perspective (compared to face-to-face or CATI interviews) justified the adoption of the CAWI modality. The same modality was applied in earlier surveys in Switzerland and in France.¹⁴

1.3.2 Survey set-up

In the design phase, the questionnaire, the consent form, and all the visual information material about CERN, including the video, were circulated among the research team in English. Once an agreement on all the documents to be submitted to respondents was reached, they were all translated into the official languages of the target countries and subtitles in local languages were added to the videos. Within the consortium, we were able to verify the accuracy of the Italian, English, and German versions with the involvement of native speakers; mother-tongue people carried out the translations for the Hebrew, Polish and Japanese versions of the documents. Afterwards, the individual versions were put in the official languages on the survey platform used by CINT. This localisation effort is important to make it easier for respondents to answer, since individuals may be more willing to respond if they can use their national language and to provide open-ended, free-text comments to explain their answers and provide clarifying rationales.

1.3.3 Pilot test

A pilot launch was run before the full survey rollout. The objective was to test the clarity of the questions, the questionnaires' length, the proper functioning of the online survey under real conditions, and the correct design of the bidding scheme, including the level of the bid asked (see Section 4 and Annex III).

The pilot test was run by reaching people with different socioeconomic traits to check the validity and the consistency of the answers along the sections of the questionnaire, and the willingness to respond from heterogeneous groups of persons. 239 pilot interviews were implemented, with the following distribution by country: 39 in the UK, 36 in Japan, Poland, and Germany, 31 in Israel and the USA, 20 in Italy. These interviews were performed in addition to the agreed sample size in each country.

Responses from the pilot tests were examined and the questionnaire was fine-tuned based on the feedback from respondents. For instance, the level of some bids in Poland was increased (because

¹⁴ In France, 88% of interviews were performed via CAWI; in contrast 12% face-to-face. Indeed, in 2018 the share of households with a web access in the country was 88%.

of the extremely higher percentages of “yes” answers), in contrast, some bids in Japan were decreased for the opposite reason and recalibrated on the per-capita GDP in the country.

1.3.4 Large scale survey

The survey was conducted during three months between September and November 2022. This phase consisted of several activities listed below:

1. Access by CINT to a web panel of respondents in each country adequate to the respective agreed sample size. The CINT web panel consists of a database of potential respondents who earlier declared that they would have been willing to cooperate for future data collection if selected. **Actual respondents to the survey were randomly selected** from this panel in compliance with the key five parameters characterising our sampling strategy. No other criteria related to CERN, or scientific research in general, were applied to avoid distortions in the composition of the sample.
2. Once identified, respondents were sent an e-mail introducing the survey and its content along with the consent form to be signed electronically. All the respondents’ consent forms were collected and delivered to CERN¹⁵.
3. Before accessing the survey, respondents were asked to pass a screening test to check their eligibility for the survey, and specifically being between the ages 18 and 75, and not being employed in market research and/or marketing.
4. If the eligibility criteria were met, the respondent was given access to the online survey, with an expected duration of 30 minutes.

1.3.5 Quality assurance and monitoring

After the launch of the survey, the evolution of the number of responses was accurately followed to be sure that the key parameters of the population were respected as precisely as possible. The survey in each country was closed when the number of respondents reached the target sample size and the size of the population parameters were met.

Received answers were submitted to the following quality checks:

- Removal of interview entries with the same sequence of answers (duplicates) and their replacement with newly carried out interviews;
- Removal of interviews entries completed in a very short time as compared to the expected duration (less than 10 minutes vs an average of 27 minutes) and replacement with newly carried out interviews;
- In very few cases, the share of respondents did not match with the share of the population key parameters (see Annex IV). For example, in the USA the percentage of people aged between 18 and 24 years is 6%, while in the sample of respondents, this share is underrepresented (2%). Weights are provided to perfectly align the sample to the population for each category of persons for each parameter (Annex IV). Preliminary statistical analysis reveals that there are no significant differences in the following results when using or not using the weights.

¹⁵ Deliverable N. 3

2. ATTITUDES TOWARDS SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

Section A of the questionnaire included questions about the general interests towards scientific research as well as its relevance for the respondents.

The first question asked people how much they were interested in the topics listed in Table 4, including physics, on a scale from “not interested at all” to “much interested”. Table 4 shows the percentage of respondents interested or very interested in the corresponding topic by country. **Only a small share of population is interested in physics-related topics, with percentages going from 13% in Poland, 15% in Japan to 25% in the USA.** In contrast, topics regarding the environment, politics and society, sports, and - to a lesser extent - arts and culture attract the interest of most of the population, regardless of the county. Internet and social media, followed by TV are the most used media to get information on the topics that people are interested in, at the expense of newspapers and books (see Table 5). By far the most engaging topic is environment.

Social media and the internet are the dominant sources of information for the population. Print media rang amongst the least consulted information sources.

Table 4. Percentage of respondents interested in listed topics

	Average %	Germany %	Italy %	Poland %	UK %	Israel %	US %	Japan %
Environment	45.71	53	58	43	49	41	49	27
Politics and Society	41.71	55	33	46	40	39	45	34
Sports	41.29	42	43	42	47	40	45	30
Arts and culture	38.00	30	45	34	36	45	42	34
Medicine	33.29	40	33	30	27	37	39	27
Astronomy	26.86	26	30	20	29	24	38	21
Biology	25.43	30	24	20	26	29	32	17
Physics	20.43	22	20	13	23	25	25	15
Geology	18.86	22	22	12	20	16	26	14

Sources: Authors. Total sample: n=1'000 in each country, n=2'000 in the USA. Questionnaire, Question A.1. How much are you interested in the following topics? Answer the questions by ticking the box corresponding to your choice. It was a five-point Likert question with possible options: Not at all; Very little; Little; Enough; Much. In the Table, interested people are those one who ticked the options 'Enough' and 'Much'. In contrast, non-interested people are those ones who ticked either 'Not at all', 'Very little', 'little'.

Table 5. Percentage of respondents often using several media

	Average %	Germany %	Italy %	Poland %	UK %	Israel %	US %	Japan %
Internet, social media	74.86	77	78	85	67	84	69	64
Television	65.86	69	72	63	67	65	69	56
Radio	33.86	47	36	43	35	33	32	11
Books	30.14	32	37	37	31	32	29	13
Newspaper	26.57	33	32	22	28	26	23	22

Sources: Authors. Total sample: n=1'000 in each country, n=2'000 in the USA. Questionnaire, Question A.2. How often do you watch/read the media below to follow news on topics that you are interest in? Possible options were “Never”, “Occasionally”, “Often”. In the Table, the share of respondents who ticked “Often” were reported.

In the next step we asked respondents about how important scientific research (fundamental, curiosity driven science as opposed to "applied research" that is specific and directly application oriented) is for them. They were asked about their agreement according to the statements listed in Table 6. Overall, respondents agree that **scientific research is important for improving quality of life** (from 46% in Poland to 60% in Italy) and **securing the future of the next generations** (from 40% in Poland to 54 in Italy). The importance of scientific research to satisfy human curiosity about the nature and origin of the universe is recognised with percentages ranging from 35% in Germany to 47% in Italy. In this context, Japan is an outlier, with percentages of agreement less than 20% whatever question submitted. In general, it is important to note that **respondents appreciate both the use value of scientific research**, i.e., for a tangible and immediate benefits such as the support of economic growth, employment and creation of new products and services, including employment, and **the non-use value**. The latter points to non-tangible and long-term benefits, such as the satisfaction of curiosity about unanswered questions concerning the origins and working of the universe.

Table 6. Percentage of respondents who agree with the listed statements

Scientific research is important to...	Average %	Germany %	Italy %	Poland %	UK %	Israel %	US %	Japan %
...improve health and quality of life	47.71	50	60	46	50	57	51	20
...secure the future of next generations	42	45	54	40	41	50	44	20
...satisfy human curiosity about the nature and origin of the Universe	35	35	47	38	37	36	38	14
...encourage the creation of new products and services	35.71	37	44	33	38	42	41	15
...support economic growth and employment	32.71	32	38	33	32	43	37	14

Sources: Authors. Total sample: n=1'000 in each country, n=2'000 in the USA. Questionnaire, Question A.3. For each statement, answer the question by ticking the box corresponding to your choice. It was a five-point Likert question with possible options: Strongly disagree; Disagree; No opinion; Agree; Strongly agree. In the Table, Agree adds up 'Agree' and 'Strongly agree' answers. Disagree is the sum of 'Strongly disagree', 'Disagree', 'No opinion'.

3. AWARENESS ABOUT CERN

Section B of the questionnaire investigated the respondents' level of awareness of CERN. The awareness of CERN was analysed by asking respondents to select which organisations they had heard about among a list of international and national organisations. That question was asked before exposing the respondents to the CERN information material (see below). Figure 1 divides respondents into three segments according to their country: US, Japan and all the other countries that are members of CERN including France and Switzerland surveyed previously. The awareness of CERN was lower in the US (29%) and in Japan (12%) than in the member states (47%). In general, the most known organisations are NASA (83% in US, 87% in Japan and 85% among CERN members), the WHO - World Health Organization - (72% in US, 86% in Japan and 80% elsewhere) and the UNESCO (37% in US, 57% in Japan and 81% among CERN members). The level of awareness of CERN is highest in the European countries, especially in Switzerland (81%) and Italy (64%); in contrast, it is lowest in non-EU countries, namely Israel, the United States and Japan (Figure 2). Annex V reports the details of the answers collected, including also national organisations. Web, social media and TV are the most important media through which respondents have heard about what CERN is and its mission (Table 7). CERN is better known than the European Space Agency (ESA) in all surveyed countries.

Figure 1. Percentage of respondents who are aware of the international organisations

Sources: Authors. Total sample: n=10'448 (including France and Switzerland). IMF: International Monetary Fund; FAO: Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations; ESA: European Spatial Agency; ITER: International Thermonuclear Experimental Reactor; ESRF; European Synchrotron Radiation Facility.

Figure 2 - Percentage of respondents who are aware of CERN by country

Sources: Authors. Total sample: n=10,448 (including France and Switzerland).

Table 7. Source of information about CERN

You know CERN because of...	Average %	US %	Japan %	CERN Members %
Web and social media, TV	20.33	20	9	32
Books and specialised magazines	10.67	9	4	19
Films and documentaries	8	8	2	14
Word of mouth	7.33	7	2	13
During my studies	6	5	2	11
Visited CERN	1	1	0	2
During my job	1.67	2	1	2
Cultural Events	1	1	-	2
Not aware of CERN	71	72	88	53

Sources: Authors. Total sample: n=10'448 (including France and Switzerland).

Question A.6 asked people, who were already aware of CERN, to write down the first thing that comes to their mind when thinking about CERN. Question A.7 asked them for a general judgment on a five-point scale going from 1 (negative) to 5 (positive). These two questions were re-submitted to the whole sample of people in Section B of the questionnaire (question B.1 and B.2, respectively) after having submitted to respondents a two-page information leaflet and a two-minute video explaining what CERN is, its research mission and achievements (information material).

Table 8 (Panel a) summarises the results of this exercise, while further details are reported in Annex V. **The positive opinion about CERN increases after having read the brochure and watched the video** that was provided for the survey: the after-before difference of the overall score is always positive in each country, except for Japan, which records a mildly negative value (-0.13). Table 8 (Panel B) also shows the percentage of respondents with positive and negative opinions within each country after exposure to the information material. **The mean score obtained always exceeded the threshold of 3.70**, which is considered the benchmark for evaluation studies based on surveys. The highest score is in Italy (4.58), followed by Poland, which showed a substantial increase after the submission of information material (4.44), and the USA (4.41). The lowest score is in Japan (3.86). Even if it is lower than in other countries, the mean score in that country is still above the threshold of 3.70. Negative opinions never exceed 3% of respondents.

The analysis of the quoted beliefs before and after the provision of the information deliverable sheds light on the increase in the overall opinion (they are all listed in Annex V by county). The three most frequent answers are “particle accelerator”, “nuclear research” and “scientific research”. The order of mentions varies slightly across countries. “Particle accelerator” comes first in Germany, the UK, the USA and Israel. “Nuclear research” is the most quoted statement in Japan and Poland, while “scientific research” comes first in Italy, Switzerland, and France. After the submission of the information material, “scientific research”, “development/innovation”, and “the possibility of a better future” jumped in the first three positions, contributing to explain to the increase of the positive perceptions.

Table 8. Opinion about of CERN - before /after comparison (%)

	Germany %	Italy %	Poland %	UK %	France %	Switzerland %	Israel %	USA %	Japan %
PANEL A: Overall Score									
MEAN SCORE AFTER EXPOSURE (Total sample - Min 1; Max 5)	4.25	4.58	4.44	4.34	4.13	4.28	4.29	4.41	3.73
MEAN SCORE BEFORE EXPOSURE (sub-sample "Aware of CERN" - Min 1; Max 5)	4.09	4.49	4.18	4.10	4.01	4.23	4.19	4.10	3.86
Difference AFTER - BEFORE	+0.16	+0.09	+0.26	+0.24	+ 0.12	+0.05	+0.10	+0.31	-0.13
PANEL B: % of respondents with ...									
Positive opinion (score = 5)	46	74	58	52	39	52	53	61	23
Somewhat positive opinion (score = 4)	36	12	30	32	39	27	25	22	30
Neutral opinion (score = 3)	16	12	11	15	19	18	20	14	43
Rather negative opinion (score = 2)	1	1	1	1	2	3	1	1	2
Negative opinion (score = 1)	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1

Sources: Authors. Total sample: n=10'448 (including France and Switzerland).

The questionnaire also asked what respondents did not like about CERN. While the percentage of respondents with a negative opinion of CERN was very low, “excessive cost”, “low safety”, “lack of communication/information”, and “subject too complex/difficult to understand” were in the top four statements mentioned (See Annex V for details). Almost all Japanese respondents mentioned that such a topic was much too difficult to understand, which partially explains the different results of this country compared to the others, together with their low awareness of CERN and interest in the subject.

The last questions of Section B were asked after all respondents had looked at the information material. These questions focussed on CERN scientific research and asked interviewees to express their level of agreement with each statement listed in Table 9. The great majority of people agree that scientific research at CERN advances our knowledge of the universe (from 79% in Israel to 86% in Switzerland) develops products for improving quality of life, including technologies for the diagnosis and treatment of diseases (70% on average across countries), CERN training programmes for students and young professionals create value for society (70%, as well). Respondents also agree that the scientific research activity at CERN should be intensified over the coming decades, with a percentage from 65% in Israel to 75% in Italy. This is in line with the fact that interviewees think that CERN is important for everyone and not only for scientists and people living in the surrounding area (Table 10).

Table 9. Percentage of respondents who agree with the following statements

	Germany %	Italy %	Poland %	UK %	France %	Switzerland %	Israel %	USA %	Japan %
CERN's discoveries allow us to enrich our knowledge of the origins and evolution of the Universe	85	82	85	83	83	86	79	81	60
CERN's discoveries can lead to the creation of products that could improve the quality of life	76	80	83	80	79	78	78	81	58
CERN's education programs for students and young professionals creates value for society	70	81	83	78	73	75	72	77	55
CERN develops new technologies for the diagnosis and treatment of diseases	63	66	73	70	77	75	66	70	50
I am proud that my country is part of the CERN international scientific research projects	62	80	77	73	67	66	71	66	45
Research activity at CERN should be intensified over the coming decades	69	75	70	65	67	67	65	66	50
Research at CERN has a positive effect on my everyday life	50	55	55	52	46	40	51	60	43
CERN's research activities contribute to peace in the world	42	47	49	51	40	30	42	55	45
CERN is a humanitarian aid organization	34	45	40	48	43	26	39	55	32

Source: Total sample: n=1'000 in each country, n=2'000 in the USA. *Questionnaire, Question B.4 and B.6.* For each of the following statements, tick the box corresponding to your choice. The question was a five-point Likert question with possible answers: Strongly disagree; Disagree; Neutral; Agree; Strongly Agree. In the Table, 'Agree' percentages are the sum of people who ticked the options 'Agree' and 'Strongly Agree'. In contrast, 'Disagree' percentages are the sum of people who ticked either 'Strongly disagree', 'Disagree', 'Neutral'.

Table 10. Percentage of respondents who agree with the following statements

Scientific research at CERN ...	Germany %	Italy %	Poland %	UK %	France %	Switzerland %	Israel %	USA %	Japan %
... is important for everyone	72	83	84	79	83	79	74	79	54
... is important for scientists only	33	16	28	25	29	26	23	24	27
... is important only for people living in the surrounding area	20	14	17	24	26	14	16	25	17
... is dangerous for the environment	15	14	15	18	20	13	16	19	15

Source: Total sample: n=1'000 in each country, n=2'000 in the USA. *Questionnaire, Question B.5* For each of the following statements, tick the box corresponding to your choice. The question was a five-point Likert question with possible answers: Strongly disagree; Disagree; Neutral; Agree; Strongly Agree. In the Table, 'Agree' percentages are the sum of people who ticked the options 'Agree' and 'Strongly Agree'. In contrast, 'Disagree' percentages are the sum of people who ticked either 'Strongly disagree', 'Disagree', 'Neutral'.

4. WILLINGNESS TO FINANCIALLY PARTICIPATE (WTP)

This section presents **if and how much CERN's future scientific research is worth to a layperson in financial (monetary) terms**. This is monetised through the concept of Willingness To financially Participate (WTP). WTP indicates the amount of money respondents would be willing to annually pay to continue research in particle physics with a new particle accelerator. The rules of the CV approach guide the quantification of the WTP.

4.1 The elicitation procedure

Section C of the questionnaire introduced respondents to the hypothetical scenarios they were asked to pay for. A preamble informed respondents about the progress particle accelerators have permitted in particle physics so far, and delivered the information that CERN is an intergovernmental organisation funded by its member states through indirect annual taxation of its residents, according to a share calculated on their respective national GDP (Figure 3). As one of the aims of the project was to understand whether the information about the actual tax contribution per capita has an influence on the citizens' stated WTP, at the end of the preamble, half of the respondents of each member were informed about the actual amount per capita already paid per year by the respective country. That information was not shared with the other half of the sample. USA and Japan are not CERN member states, implying that they do not contribute to the CERN annual budget with in-cash tax contribution. Therefore, there is no information on the tax contribution.¹⁶ However, they are part of the LHC research programme and the FCC international feasibility study collaboration¹⁷.

Two scenarios were submitted to respondents: one with the investment taking place, and one with no investment taking place. For member states (Germany, Israel, Italy, Poland, and United Kingdom), Scenario A is the investment scenario, and scenario B is the non-investment scenario. For the non-member states USA and Japan a slightly different phrasing has been chosen for the two scenarios: the term "member states" has been replaced with the term "international collaboration", leading to two equivalent scenarios C and D. Scenario C (equivalent to scenario A) is the investment scenario, and scenario D (equivalent to scenario B) is the non-investment scenario. Respondents were asked to financially contribute to the investment scenario.

¹⁶ The previous Swiss survey was conducted in the same way, while during the French one, no citizen was informed about the actual tax contribution per capita.

¹⁷ The USA and Japan contribute with in-kind contributions but cannot be compared to the annual contribution of member states because of different logic. Therefore, no information about the actual contribution was shared with respondents in the USA and Japan.

Figure 3. Preamble

Particle accelerator research, including the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) at CERN, has established a theoretical representation of the Universe. However, the research highlights phenomena that cannot be explained by this theory.

CERN Member States, including 'COUNTRY NAME', are financing this research. Here are two possible scenarios for the future of this research.

[Only for CERN Member States:]

Each 'NATIONALITY' person over the age of 18 pay on average about 'AMOUNT IN LOCAL CURRENCY' per year to CERN through taxes.

Figure 3 Hypothetical scenarios to elicit the WTP for CERN particle physics research.

Scenario A

CERN Member States decide to invest in a new particle accelerator in the next decade. It will make discoveries on phenomena that cannot be explained today. This new accelerator will be operated for at least twenty-five years.

Scenario B

CERN Member States decide not to invest in a new particle accelerator. The research activity with the existing accelerator, the LHC, will gradually decrease over the next twenty years. The possibility of finding answers on unexplained phenomena will remain limited.

Scenario C

The CERN international collaboration decides to invest in a new particle accelerator in the next decade. It will make discoveries on phenomena that cannot be explained today. This new accelerator will be operated for at least twenty-five years.

Scenario D

The CERN international Collaboration decides not to invest in a new particle accelerator. The research activity with the existing accelerator, the LHC, will gradually decrease over the next twenty years. The possibility of finding answers on unexplained phenomena will remain limited.

Notes: English translation of the original scenarios that were phrased in the local languages of the countries in which the survey was administered. In original scenarios, 'COUNTRY NAME' is replaced with the name of the State of the respondent. Source: Questionnaire, Section C.

After the introduction of scenarios, the WTP question was asked:

'Would you agree to pay the amount of X per year as a taxpayer for the construction of a new particle accelerator at CERN as described in scenario 'A/C?'

where the amount X was the proposed bid in local currency, i.e., the price the individual is asked to pay. The bid was pre-printed in the questionnaire, while the statement "as a taxpayer" was included in all questionnaires to increase the credibility of the questionnaire reflecting the fact that only public contributions enable CERN to continue its research activity.¹⁸ Accordingly, the hypothetical payment vehicle used for this study was taxation, which all the respondents are likely to be familiar with.

In CV studies, two types of approaches can be used to estimate the WTP: firstly, the single-bounded dichotomous choice approach, also known as 'referendum-like' approach. People are only asked to answer 'yes' or 'no' to a proposed bid. In the case of the WTP question above, the referendum-like question would be:

*'Would you agree to pay the amount of X per year as a taxpayer for the construction of a new particle accelerator at CERN as described in scenario A/C?'
with possible answers being 'yes' or 'no'.*

The main advantage of the referendum-like approach is that it mirrors the working of the market: when one wants to buy a good, one takes it or leaves it based on its price. If the price is accepted, then it makes no sense to ask to pay more. The disadvantage of this approach is that it prevents from estimating the lower bounds and the upper bounds of individual WTP and even the maximum WTP. For instance, respondents who say 'no' may still have a positive WTP, but lower than the proposed bid. Similarly, respondents who say 'yes' may have higher WTP.

The second approach is the so-called double-bounded dichotomous choice approach. It stresses the importance of follow-up questions to have a more accurate quantification of the WTP. In practice, the bid level offered in the follow-up questions should be higher than the offered bid in the initial payment if the answer to the initial payment question is 'yes'; in contrast, if the answer is 'no', a lower bid is offered.

In this study, the double-bounded dichotomous choice was used. A third follow-up question was added to detect the maximum WTP and properly identify zero WTPs¹⁹. In practice, five versions of the questionnaire (A, B, C, D, and E), which only varied in the amount of the initial bid (and consequently lower and upper bids), were randomly submitted to respondents in each country²⁰. Figure 4 shows the bidding scheme used for Germany. For instance, version C of the questionnaire asked to pay CHF 17 to support investment scenario A. The lower amount of CHF 6 was asked in the follow-up question in case of a 'no' answer to the initial bid of CHF 17; in contrast, if the answer was 'yes', the amount of CHF 33 was asked. Each version was randomly allocated to a sub-sample of about 20% of the people interviewed in each country, whose internal demographic distribution mirrors that of the entire country sample.

¹⁸ See [3; 4; 14].

¹⁹ See [15]. Moreover, see [14] for a recent discussion on single-bounded vs double-bounded dichotomous choice approaches.

²⁰ Initial, lower and upper bids were determined by the results of the pilot, the pre-tests as mentioned in Section 2.

Figure 4. Example of the bidding scheme (Germany, local currency converted to CHF)

Source: Authors.

Those respondents who said ‘no’ to the initial bids (e.g., CHF 17) can be divided into two groups: those who really had a zero WTP and those who had a positive WTP that is lower than the second lowest bid (e.g., between CHF 0 and CHF 6). Similarly, people who said ‘yes’ to the initial bid (of CHF 17) could have an even higher WTP. Therefore, a third open follow-up question was asked to each respondent to detect the maximum WTP. Specifically, they were asked:

‘What is your maximum annual amount you would pay for supporting scenario A/C?’

Figure 5 illustrates a complete example (Version C, starting with CHF 17) of the payment mechanism to elicit the WTP for investments in particle physics research at CERN. Whatever the path followed by respondents, close-ended questions were asked to motivate the stated WTP amount²¹.

21 See questions C.4 and C.6 of the questionnaire.

Figure 5. Payment mechanism (Bid C, Germany), local currency converted to CHF

BID C

Starting point: CHF 17

Source: Authors.

4.2 Results

4.2.1 The quantification of the WTP

Table 11 shows the value of the WTP stated by respondents when the question about the maximum annual amount willing to pay to support the investment scenario is asked.

Column (1) lists the country by distinguishing CERN member states from non-member states, and for member states the average contribution per capita in 2021 is reported (column 2). For instance, in the UK, each adult person paid CHF 4 in 2021 via tax contribution, while in Poland it was CHF 1 per person²². The percentage of respondents who already knew CERN before the provision of the information material is indicated in column 3. Column 4 reports the share of respondents that declared a positive WTP (different from zero) by country.

The WTP stated by respondents is reported in the next columns, by distinguishing between WTP calculated on the entire sample of respondents (column 5) or only on the share of respondents with a positive WTP (column 6). For the latter group, clearly the mean and median WTP values are higher, because respondents with a WTP equal to zero have been excluded. The maximum WTP declared in each state is shown in column 7²³. The complete WTP distributions in each country are visualised in Annex IV.

²² The average contribution per capita corresponds to the ratio between the total financial contribution to the CERN budget by that country in 2021 and its total population over 18 years old.

²³ WTP statistics always exclude outliers (too enthusiastic respondents) with a ratio between the stated WTP and income above 0.5% (five per thousands). In contrast, respondents with zero WTP are included when estimates are made for the entire sample of respondents.

The table shows the following findings:

- The stated WTP varies among countries, ranging from CHF 0 to a maximum of CHF 551 in Italy and from CHF 0 to CHF 77 in Poland. The maximum is even higher in the USA. The variability is explained by the socioeconomic characteristics of individual respondents in each country, which will be further explained below.
- **The mean WTP per person is always above the annual tax contribution per capita pointing to the fact that the value of CERN's scientific research perceived by respondents is larger than they actually pay (columns 5 and 6 vs column 2).** This holds true even when the median is considered for the comparison as a more conservative quantification of the WTP than the mean²⁴. The above statement is also corroborated by the statistic stability of the WTP quantification: the provision of information about the actual tax contribution to only half of the sample of respondents in each country has not influenced the stated WTP. There are no differences in mean and median between the subsamples of respondents who received that information compared to those who did not. In general, **the mean and median WTPs are larger in those countries with a larger share of respondents who were already aware of CERN and its research activities.** In Switzerland (one of two CERN hosting countries) the mean and the median WTP are respectively CHF 55 and CHF 20 with an 80% share of respondents who knew CERN before the survey; in contrast, Japan has a mean WTP of CHF 10 and a median WTP of CHF 0 with a share of respondents aware of CERN of 13%. **The lack of knowledge about CERN also determines the larger percentages of respondents with zero WTP in some countries such as France.**

Table 11. Stated annual WTP, awareness of CERN and percentage of zero WTP

(1) Country	(2) Average tax contribution per person in 2021	(3) Respondents aware of CERN	(4) Respondents with WTP > 0	(5) WTP per person of all respondents		(6) WTP per person (only respondents with WTP>0)		(7) Max. WTP per person	(8) Total N of respondents	(9) Year of the survey
				Mean	Median	Mean	Median			
	CHF	%	%	CHF	CHF	CHF	CHF	CHF	N	Y
CERN member states										
Switzerland	6	80	73	55	20	67	50	500	1'000	2019
UK	4	44	77	30	14	39	19	303	1'053	2022
Italy	2	65	76	29	13	38	22	551	1'084	2022
Germany	3	39	69	20	11	29	22	221	1'027	2022
Israel	3	28	68	16	6	23	15	233	1'094	2022
France	3	46	52	4 - 14	2	28	11	355	1'005	2018
Poland	1	38	77	9	6	12	10	77	1'072	2022
CERN non-member states										
USA	zero	27	73	44	24	61	48	672	2'048	2022
Japan	zero	13	29	10	0	35	18	496	1'065	2022

Source: Authors.

²⁴ In each country, the difference between the mean and the median of the WTP distribution is due to its skewness towards the left which makes the mean larger than the median.

The reasons why citizens are willing to financially contribute to CERN scientific research are listed by country in Table 12. Overall, considering the total number of respondents, they can be grouped in order of importance as follows:

- **Curiosity** was selected by 52% of respondents, who see research at CERN as a means to answer unanswered questions about the universe even if this activity does not necessarily lead to tangible or concrete application (green rows)²⁵.
- 42% of respondents were willing to contribute because they think that scientific research at CERN **improves skills and competencies of people** (yellow rows).
- **Industry-related benefits** was the motivation of a positive WTP for 20% of respondents (red row).
- Lastly, **geographic-related benefits**, including world (grey rows) were also mentioned by 49% of respondents.

Table 12. Main reasons for being ready to financially participate (WTP > 0)

Reason	Germany	Israel	Italy	Japan	Poland	UK	USA	France	Switzerland
I think that CERN's activities justify at least this amount	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	49%	13%
I feel humanity has a duty to push the frontier of knowledge ahead	20%	44%	44%	26%	24%	34%	32%	0%	0%
Always support CERN research even if no concrete/tangible application	26%	26%	15%	38%	32%	23%	25%	23%	19%
Competencies/skills of all people involved in the projects will grow	13%	12%	12%	11%	11%	12%	14%	14%	8%
CERN research advances knowledge in STEM subjects	46%	31%	42%	47%	34%	38%	35%	-	-
Research enables companies to develop new products and services	20%	22%	17%	31%	21%	21%	25%	23%	17%
Benefits for France	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	17%	-
Benefits for Switzerland	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	21%
Benefits for Europe	20%	8%	12%	3%	17%	13%	5%	6%	7%
Benefits for the entire world	40%	37%	32%	19%	43%	39%	40%	36%	34%
Other reasons	1%	1%	1%	1%	1%	2%	1%	2%	2%
Sub sample of respondents with WTP > 0 (N)	609	620	758	310	700	685	1,411	497	705

Source: Authors. Notes: Questions C.6. of the questionnaire. Multiple answers question. Outliers are excluded. The total sample size of respondents with WTP > 0 is 6'295.

²⁵ The reason “I think that CERN's activities justify at least this amount” was asked in the first experiments in France and Switzerland. It was replaced in later surveys with clearer reasons.

About one third (3'252 out of 10'448) of the respondents stated a WTP of zero (Table 13). **Among the reasons for not contributing, unaffordability represents the first motive with 37% of respondents stating that they were not able to afford the amount asked (green row), followed by the preference to spend their money for alternative purposes (26%) or research (21%), while 25% of respondents stated a zero WTP because either did not understand the purpose of scientific research at CERN or thought that only persons who benefit from CERN research should pay for it (light blue). Protest answers (general opposition) are infrequent, i.e., those persons who would have responded zero in any case regardless of CERN only amount to 8%.**

Table 13. Main reasons for not wishing to financially participate (WTP = 0)

Reason for not financially participating: WTP=0	Germany	Israel	Italy	Japan	Poland	UK	USA	France	Switzerland
Currently, I cannot afford this expense	43%	29%	39%	53%	38%	36%	41%	56%	13%
I prefer to spend my money on other things	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	39%	9%
I prefer that my tax contribution is used for other uses	21%	25%	19%	16%	27%	22%	21%	-	-
I think my taxes contribution should be used to fund other research activities	9%	10%	13%	8%	8%	15%	11%	11%	5%
I think my money should be used to fund research in my own country	7%	12%	7%	15%	12%	12%	13%	-	-
I am against government-funded programs	10%	9%	3%	2%	5%	7%	6%	4%	3%
I am against international organizations	3%	2%	3%	1%	2%	3%	3%	2%	1%
I do not understand the purpose of CERN's scientific research	9%	12%	7%	14%	7%	11%	14%	9%	5%
Only people who directly benefit from CERN research should pay for it	12%	17%	7%	9%	7%	11%	6%	7%	6%
Other reasons	6%	6%	10%	7%	3%	5%	7%	8%	4%
Subsample of respondents with WTP = 0 (N)	277	296	242	741	208	205	524	495	264

Source: Authors. Notes: Questions C.4. of the questionnaire. Multiple answers question. The total sample size of respondents with WTP = 0 is 3'252.

4.2.2 The determinants of the WTP

The respondents' **socioeconomic characteristics and attitudes towards scientific research play a key role for the WTP**. Table 14 shows the relationship between the stated WTP, and some relevant traits of interviewees measured by correlation coefficients. Asterisks associated with that characteristic indicate the existence of a statistical association with WTP.

The higher the income, the higher the willingness for financial contribution of respondents; similarly, being male is associated with a larger WTP. This is a pattern that has been identified for the physics science domain, which is still a male-dominated field of research. **People with a tertiary education level (high) are willing to contribute more** than persons with lower education. Also, **employed persons are willing to contribute more** than unemployed people or students, who in general have less available income. **The family size does not influence the WTP.**

In addition to demographics, **personal interests and existing opinions also make a difference. Persons who want to support curiosity-driven research, including the fact that CERN scientific research contributes to advancing knowledge or should be intensified in the future, stated higher WTP compared to people who do not. The awareness of CERN and its scientific research mission is a key motivator of the WTP value.**

Figure 6 visualises the relationship between the mean and median WTP vis à vis the pre-capita GDP in the country, while Figure 7 shows the relationship with CERN awareness. In both cases, there is a significant positive association with WTP pointing to the importance of these two drivers of the citizens' involvement in CERN matters.

Table 14. Determinant factors of the WTP

Variable	Correlation coefficient
Income (RELEVANT)	
Low	-0.14***
Medium	0.05***
High	0.11***
Gender (RELEVANT)	
Male	0.06***
Female	-0.06***
Age (MODERATELY RELEVANT)	
Less than 35	-0.02**
More than 35	0.02**
Occupational Status (RELEVANT)	
Employed	0.03**
Retired	0.04***
Unemployed	-0.1***
Student	-0.1***
Education level (RELEVANT)	
Low	-0.04***
Medium	-0.06***
High	0.09***
Family Size (NOT RELEVANT)	
1 member	0.001
2-3 members	0.0172
More than 3 members	-0.01
Personal interests and awareness of CERN (HIGHLY RELEVANT and IMPACTFUL)	
Having interest for science and research	0.25***
Being aware of CERN	0.2***
CERN permits an increase in knowledge of universe	0.29***
The research activity at CERN should increase in the coming decades	0.34***
Curiosity	0.08***

Notes: Statistical significance level *** $p < 0.01$, ** $p < 0.05$, * $p < 0$. Source: Authors.

Figure 6 Relationship between (Mean and Median) WTP and awareness of CERN

Source: Authors.

Figure 7 Relationship between (Mean and Median) WTP and GDP per capita

Source: Authors.

REFERENCES

- [1.] **Alberini A. and Longo A. (2006).** Combining the Travel Cost and Contingent Behavior Methods to Value Cultural Heritage Sites: Evidence from Armenia, *Journal of Cultural Economics*, 30(4): 287-304.
- [2.] **Amirnejad, H., Khalilian, S., Assareh, M.H. and Ahmadian, M. (2006).** Estimating the Existence Value of North Forests of Iran by Using a Contingent Valuation Method, *Ecological Economics*, 58(4), 665-675.
- [3.] **Arrow, K., Solow, R.S., Learner, E., Portney, P., Rodner, R. and Schuman, H. (1993).** Report of the NOAA-Panel on Contingent Valuation, *Federal Register*, 58(10), 4601-4614.
- [4.] **Carson, R.T., Mitchell, R.C., Hanemann, M., Kopp, R.J., Presser, S., and Ruud, P.A. (2003).** Contingent Valuation and Lost Passive Use: Damages from the Exxon Valdez Oil Spill, *Environmental and resource economics*, 25(3), 257-286.
- [5.] **De-Magistris T, Gracia A, Nayga RM Jr.** On the use of honesty priming tasks to mitigate hypothetical bias in choice experiments. *American Journal of Agricultural Economics*. 2013; 95: 1136-1154 <https://doi.org/10.1093/ajae/aat052>
- [6.] **Florio, M., & Giffoni, F. (2018).** Scientific Research at CERN as a Public Good: A Survey to French Citizens (No. CERN-ACC-2018-0024). FCC-DRAFT-ENG-2018-008.
- [7.] **Florio, M., & Giffoni, F. (2020).** A contingent valuation experiment about future particle accelerators at CERN. *PloS one*, 15(3), e0229885.
- [8.] **Frey B.S. (2003).** *Arts and Economics. Analysis & Cultural Policy*, Heidelberg, DE: Springer-Verlag.
- [9.] **Giffoni, F., & Florio, M. (2023).** Public support of science: A contingent valuation study of citizens' attitudes about CERN with and without information about implicit taxes. *Research Policy*, 52(1), 104627.
- [10.] **Green, D., Jacowitz, K.E., Kahneman, D. and Mcfadden, D. (1998).** Referendum Contingent Valuation, Anchoring, and Willingness To Pay for Public Goods. *Resource and Energy Economics*, 20(2), 85-116.
- [11.] **Hansen T.B. (1997).** The Willingness-To-Pay for the Royal Theatre in Copenhagen as a Public Good, *Journal of Cultural Economics*, 21(1): 1-28.
- [12.] **Jacquemet N, James AG, Luchini S, Shogren JF.** Social psychology and environmental economics: a new look at ex ante corrections of biased preference evaluation. *Environmental and Resource Economics*. 2011; 48: 413-433 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10640-010-9448-4>
- [13.] **Jacquemet N, Joule RV, Luchini S, Shogren JF.** Preference elicitation under oath. *Journal of Environmental Economics and Management*. 2013; 65: 110-132 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jeem.2012.05.004>
- [14.] **Johnston, R.J., Boyle, K.J., Adamowicz, W., Bennett, J., Brouwer, R., Cameron, T.A., Hanemann, W.M., Hanley, N., Ryan, M., Scarpa R., Tourangeau, R., and Vossler, C.A. (2017).** Contemporary Guidance for Stated Preference Studies, *Journal of the Association of Environmental and Resource Economists*, 4(2), 319-405.
- [15.] **Kwak, S. Y., Yoo, S. H., & Kim, C. S. (2013).** Measuring the willingness to pay for tap water quality improvements: results of a contingent valuation survey in Pusan, *Water*, 5(4), 1638-1652.
- [16.] **LOPEZ-FELDMAN, A. (2012).** Introduction to contingent valuation using Stata. MPRA paper No. 41018, posted 4. https://mpa.ub.uni-muenchen.de/41018/2/MPRA_paper_41018.pdf
- [17.] **Packer J. (2008).** Beyond Learning: Exploring Visitors' Perceptions of the Value and Benefits of museum experiences, *The Museum Journal*, 51(1): 33-54.

ANNEX I - Bidding scheme in CHF

Bidding Scheme in Germany		
Initial Bid	Lower Bid	Upper Bid
3	3	6
7	4	17
17	6	33
33	17	66
66	33	133

Bidding Scheme in Poland		
Initial Bid	Lower Bid	Upper Bid
1	1	3
3	1	6
6	3	12
12	6	19
19	12	38

Bidding Scheme in USA		
Initial Bid	Lower Bid	Upper Bid
5	3	10
10	5	19
19	10	48
48	19	77
77	48	144

Bidding Scheme in Italy		
Initial Bid	Lower Bid	Upper Bid
2	1	6
6	2	11
11	6	33
33	11	55
55	33	110

Bidding Scheme in UK		
Initial Bid	Lower Bid	Upper Bid
4	3	6
6	4	13
13	6	38
38	13	63
63	38	126

Bidding Scheme in France		
Initial Bid	Lower Bid	Upper Bid
3	2	5
5	3	10
10	5	30
30	10	50
50	30	100

Bidding Scheme in Israel		
Initial Bid	Lower Bid	Upper Bid
3	2	4
4	3	10
10	4	21
21	10	42
42	21	73

Bidding Scheme in Japan		
Initial Bid	Lower Bid	Upper Bid
3	2	4
4	3	9
9	4	26
26	9	44
44	26	88

Bidding Scheme in Switzerland		
Initial Bid	Lower Bid	Upper Bid
6	3	15
15	6	30
30	15	75
75	30	150
150	75	300

Notes: France refers to 2017 and Switzerland to 2019.

ANNEX II - Consent form (English version)

Informed consent

Please, read carefully this document before participating in the survey.

Dear Sir or Madam,

We invite you to participate in an inquiry to find out your opinion on the value of the research activities carried out at CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research), an international organization whose convention was ratified in 1954 and amended by amendments in 1971.

Eumetra International SA (Cint) carries out the survey on behalf of CERN.

You are one of the people selected to form a sample of the (NAME COUNTRY) population and invited to express themselves on this subject. Your participation is therefore greatly appreciated, and your sincere opinion can help to make decisions about strengthening research activities at CERN. Please note that due to possible conflicts of interest, having or having had professional relations with CERN (contract as employee, student or associate staff member, contractual relations, activities at CERN, contractors or subcontractors) does not allow you to participate in this survey.

During this survey, CERN's research activities will be introduced to you through a video (approximately two minutes) and a short document (approximately two pages). We will then ask you to express your opinion on the research activities carried out at CERN and to indicate whether you would be ready to support new investments for this type of research. At the end of the survey, we will also ask you for some additional information, such as region of residence, age group, family size, and income class. This will allow us to read the results both in total and for the main socio-demographic traits.

The survey fully protects your privacy and guarantees the confidentiality of the information provided. Click on the link to access more information about privacy: [HERE HIPERLINK TO THE PRIVACY LAW OF THE COUNTRY](#)

If you have any questions about your rights as a participant in this survey, or if you wish to obtain additional information or to express any concerns about this survey, please contact Mr. Luca Secci, from Eumetra International SA (email address: luca.secci@eumetra.com)

In order to participate in the survey, please agree with the statements below.

- i. I declare that I have no connection with CERN (for example, former staff member, and person having business with CERN, contractor or equivalent). YES
- ii. I agree to participate in this survey. I understand the purpose and nature of this investigation and I participate voluntarily. I understand that I may stop participating in this survey at any time without penalty or consequence. YES
- iii. I understand the relevance of the results of this survey to the public. I authorize the use of the data of this interview in an anonymous and consolidated form, in accordance with the French regulations in force concerning the protection of the private life, for scientific publications on this subject. YES
- iv. I understand the relevance of this survey for CERN and for its investments in future research activities. I therefore undertake to provide honest and sincere answers. YES

By signing and returning this form, you confirm that you have read the document and agree to participate in the survey. Place and date Signature

ANNEX III - The questionnaire (UK version)

The value of particle physics research at CERN as public good A survey among taxpayers in Germany, Italy, Poland, US, Israel, Japan, and UK The Contingent Valuation questionnaire (V06 09.08.2022)

Bidding Scheme

United Kingdom (UK); Total sample N= 1 000, Currency: Pound (GBP)

Sub-samples (10 X 100 respondents each)					
Info on current tax contribution to CERN	Yes / No	Questionnaire Version	Initial bid (Question C.1)	Lower bid (Question C.2)	Upper bid (Question C.5)
GBP 3 mentioned	Yes	UKYA	GBP 3	GBP 2	GBP 5
GBP 3 mentioned	Yes	UKYB	GBP 5	GBP 3	GBP 10
GBP 3 mentioned	Yes	UKYC	GBP 10	GBP 5	GBP 30
GBP 3 mentioned	Yes	UKYD	GBP 30	GBP 10	GBP 50
GBP 3 mentioned	Yes	UKYE	GBP 50	GBP 30	GBP 100
No mention	No	UKNA	GBP 3	GBP 2	GBP 5
No mention	No	UKNB	GBP 5	GBP 3	GBP 10
No mention	No	UKNC	GBP 10	GBP 5	GBP 30
No mention	No	UKND	GBP 30	GBP 10	GBP 50
No mention	No	UKNE	GBP 50	GBP 30	GBP 100

SECTION A: YOUR INTERESTS

A.1 How much interested are you in the following topics? Answer the questions by ticking the box corresponding to your choice. [FOR THE SCRIPTER: RANDOMIZE]

	<i>Not at all</i>	<i>Not much</i>	<i>Fairly</i>	<i>Very</i>	<i>Very much</i>
A.1.1 Sports	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A.1.2 Politics and Society	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A.1.3 Biology	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A.1.4 Physics	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A.1.5 Astronomy	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A.1.6 Geology	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A.1.7 Medicine	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A.1.8 Environment	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A.1.9 Arts and culture	<input type="checkbox"/>				

A.2 How often do you watch/read the media below to follow news on topics that you are interest in? [FOR THE SCRIPTER: RANDOMIZE]

	<i>Never</i>	<i>Occasionally</i>	<i>Often</i>
A.2.1 Television	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A.2.2 Radio	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A.2.3 Newspaper	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A.2.4 Books	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
A.2.5 Internet and social media	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

A.3 For each statement, tick the box corresponding to your choice. [FOR THE SCRIPTER: RANDOMIZE]					
Scientific research is important to:	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Neutral</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Strongly agree</i>
A.3.1 Improve health and quality of life	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A.3.2 Secure the future of next generations	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A.3.3 Satisfy human curiosity about the nature and origin of the Universe	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A.3.4 Support economic growth and employment	<input type="checkbox"/>				
A.3.5 Encourage the creation of new products and services	<input type="checkbox"/>				

A.4 Which of the following organizations are you aware of? (If you tick CERN, go directly to question A.5 otherwise go to section B) [FOR THE SCRIPTER: RANDOMIZE; BEWARE CHANGES FROM THE LAST SURVEY]	FOR THE SCRIPTER: ALL COUNTRIES <input type="checkbox"/> WHO (World Health Organization) <input type="checkbox"/> NASA (National Aeronautics and Space Administration) <input type="checkbox"/> CERN (European Organization for Nuclear Research) <input type="checkbox"/> ESA (European Space Agency) <input type="checkbox"/> IMF (International Monetary Fund) <input type="checkbox"/> FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization) <input type="checkbox"/> ESRF (European Synchrotron Radiation Facility) <input type="checkbox"/> UNESCO (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization) <input type="checkbox"/> ITER (the international nuclear fusion research project)
	ONLY UK: <input type="checkbox"/> Diamond Light Source <input type="checkbox"/> CI (Cockcroft Institute) <input type="checkbox"/> UK Space Agency <input type="checkbox"/> JAI (John Adams Institute) <input type="checkbox"/> RAL (Rutherford Appleton Laboratory) <input type="checkbox"/> RI (The Royal Institution of Great Britain)

<p>A.5 Why are you aware of CERN? (multiple choice possible) [FOR THE SCRIPTER: RANDOMIZE; BEWARE CHANGES FROM THE LAST SURVEY]</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> You have heard about CERN through a person (e.g. colleagues, friends, family members, CERN employees, ...) <input type="checkbox"/> You have heard about CERN during your studies (at school, university) <input type="checkbox"/> You are aware of CERN because of your current job or professional background <input type="checkbox"/> You have participated in cultural events organized by CERN or in connection with CERN <input type="checkbox"/> You have acquired information from books, newspapers, or specialized magazines mentioning the CERN's name <input type="checkbox"/> You have watched films and/or documentaries related to CERN <input type="checkbox"/> You have heard about CERN through television, internet and social media <input type="checkbox"/> You have visited CERN <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify): _____
---	---

A.6 When you think of CERN, what does it come to your mind first?

<p>A.7 What is your opinion about CERN?</p> <p>Tick the box correspondig to your choice</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Positive <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat positive <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Rather negative <input type="checkbox"/> Negative
---	--

SECTION B: YOUR KNOWLEDGE OF CERN

Click the link to read the document on CERN: **[FOR THE SCRIPTER: Here specific link for each country]**

Click here to watch the 2-minute video about CERN: **[FOR THE SCRIPTER: Here specific link for each country]**

B.1 What aspects of CERN do you like?

B.2 What aspects of CERN do you dislike?

<p>B.3 What is your perception of CERN?</p> <p>Tick the box corresponding to your choice</p>	<input type="checkbox"/> Positive <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat positive <input type="checkbox"/> Neutral <input type="checkbox"/> Rather negative <input type="checkbox"/> Negative
--	--

B.4 For each of the following statements, tick the box corresponding to your choice [FOR THE SCRIPTER: RANDOMIZE]					
	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Neutral</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Strongly agree</i>
B.4.1 CERN develops new technologies for the diagnosis and treatment of diseases	<input type="checkbox"/>				
B.4.2 CERN's discoveries allow us to enrich our knowledge of the origins and evolution of the Universe	<input type="checkbox"/>				
B.4.3 CERN is a humanitarian aid organization	<input type="checkbox"/>				
B.4.4 CERN's discoveries can lead to the creation of products that could improve the quality of life	<input type="checkbox"/>				

B.5 For each of the following statements, tick the box corresponding to your choice [FOR THE SCRIPTER: RANDOMIZE]					
Research at CERN ...	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Neutral</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Strongly agree</i>
B.5.1... is important for scientists only	<input type="checkbox"/>				
B.5.2 ... is important for everyone	<input type="checkbox"/>				
B.5.3 ... is important only for people living in the surrounding area	<input type="checkbox"/>				

B.5.4 ... is dangerous for the environment	<input type="checkbox"/>				
---	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------	--------------------------

B.6 For each of the following statements, tick the box corresponding to your choice [FOR THE SCRIPTER: RANDOMIZE; BEWARE CHANGES FROM THE LAST SURVEY]					
	<i>Strongly disagree</i>	<i>Disagree</i>	<i>Neutral</i>	<i>Agree</i>	<i>Strongly agree</i>
B.6.1 I am proud that my country is part of the CERN international scientific research projects	<input type="checkbox"/>				
B.6.2 Research at CERN has a positive effect on my everyday life	<input type="checkbox"/>				
B.6.3 Research activity at CERN should be intensified over the coming decades	<input type="checkbox"/>				
B.6.4 CERN's education programs for students and young professionals creates value for society	<input type="checkbox"/>				
B.6.5 CERN's research activities contribute to peace in the world	<input type="checkbox"/>				

SECTION C: YOUR SUPPORT AT CERN

[FOR THE SCRIPTER: TO ALL COUNTRIES]

Particle accelerator research, including the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) at CERN, has established a theoretical representation of the Universe. However, the research highlights phenomena that cannot be explained by this theory.

CERN Member States, including the United Kingdom, are financing this research.

All British people over the age of 18 pay on average about 3 Pounds per year to CERN through taxes.

Here are two possible scenarios for the future of this research.

Scenario A

CERN Member States decides to invest in a new particle accelerator in the next decade. It will make discoveries on phenomena that cannot be explained today. This new accelerator will be operated for at least twenty-five years.

Scenario B

CERN Member States decide not to invest in a new particle accelerator. The research activity with the existing accelerator, the LHC, will gradually decrease over the next twenty years. The possibility of finding answers on unexplained phenomena will remain limited.

YOUR CHOICE

C.1 Would you agree to pay **the sum of ___ Pounds per year as a taxpayer for the construction** of a new particle accelerator at CERN as described in scenario A?

YES (Go to question C.5)

NO (Go to question C.2)

C.2 Would you agree to pay **the sum of ___ Pounds per year as a taxpayer to support the investment** in scenario A?

YES (Go to question C.3.1)

NO (Go to question C.3.2)

C.3.1 What would be your **maximum annual contribution** as a taxpayer to support this investment?

I would participate with ___ Pounds

(Go to question C.6)

C.3.2 What would be your **maximum annual amount** you would pay for supporting scenario A?

I would not participate financially
(Go to question C.4)

I would participate with ____ **Pounds**
(Go to question C.6)

C.4 Answer this question only if you answered the previous question: "I would not participate financially". What are the main reasons you would not participate financially? Choose at most two options. [FOR THE SCRIPTER: RANDOMIZE; BEWARE CHANGES FROM THE LAST SURVEY]

- I prefer that my tax contribution is used for other uses
- Currently, I cannot afford this expense
- I do not understand the purpose of CERN's scientific research. Therefore, I do not want to contribute
- I am against government-funded programs
- I am against international organizations
- I think my taxes contribution should be used to fund research activities in other fields
- Only people who directly benefit from CERN research activities should pay for it
- I think my money should be used to fund research activities in my own country
- Other reasons (specify): _____

GO TO THE SECTION D

C.5 Would you agree to pay **the sum of ____ Pounds per year as a taxpayer to support the investment** in scenario A?

YES (Go to the question C.5.1)

NO (Go to the question C.5.2)

C.5.1 What would be your **maximum annual amount** you would pay for supporting scenario A?

I would participate with ____ **Pounds**

C.5.2 What would be your **maximum annual amount** you would pay for supporting scenario A?

I would participate with ____ **Pounds**

C.6 For what reason (s), would you pay this amount? Choose at most two options.

[FOR THE SCRIPTER: BEWARE CHANGES FROM THE LAST SURVEY]

- I feel humanity has a duty to push the frontier of knowledge ahead
- Through this research the competences/skills of all people involved in the CERN activities will grow
- Research enables companies to develop new products and services
- CERN research advances knowledge in science, technology, engineering and mathematics
- I think it is fair to contribute to better understand the Universe even if the results do not necessarily lead to any concrete application
- All Europe benefits from CERN activities
- The whole world benefits from CERN activities
- Other reasons (specify): _____

SECTION D: YOUR PROFILE

D.1 You are	<input type="checkbox"/> Male <input type="checkbox"/> Female <input type="checkbox"/> Other
--------------------	--

D.2 Your age	_____ years
---------------------	-------------

D.3 Your highest level of education	<input type="checkbox"/>
	[ONLY UK] <input type="checkbox"/> no qualifications <input type="checkbox"/> lower school <input type="checkbox"/> middle school <input type="checkbox"/> high school diploma <input type="checkbox"/> university diploma/bachelor degree <input type="checkbox"/> university degree /master degree <input type="checkbox"/> post lauream (Phd, post graduate degree...)

D.4 Your highest level of education is mainly related to: [FOR THE SCRIPTER: NEW QUESTION]	<input type="checkbox"/> Arts and humanities <input type="checkbox"/> Social science, journalism and information <input type="checkbox"/> Business, administration and law <input type="checkbox"/> Natural science, mathematics and statistics <input type="checkbox"/> Information and Communication Technologies <input type="checkbox"/> Engineering, manufacturing and construction <input type="checkbox"/> Agriculture, forestry, fisheries and veterinary <input type="checkbox"/> Education <input type="checkbox"/> Health and welfare <input type="checkbox"/> Services <input type="checkbox"/> Other, please specify: _____
---	--

D.5 Your Job	<input type="checkbox"/> Executive <input type="checkbox"/> Employee <input type="checkbox"/> Worker <input type="checkbox"/> Craftsman <input type="checkbox"/> Freelance <input type="checkbox"/> Unemployed <input type="checkbox"/> Retired <input type="checkbox"/> Student <input type="checkbox"/> Researcher <input type="checkbox"/> Engineer <input type="checkbox"/> Teacher/professor <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify): _____
---------------------	--

D.6 The region where you live [FOR THE SCRIPTER: USE SINGLE REGIONS, THEN RECODE IN MACRO AREAS]	[ONLY UK] Scroll down menu with NUTS2 regions						
---	---	--	--	--	--	--	--

ANNEX IV - Sample demographics vs country population

The percentage indicates how close the sample of respondents is to the population in each country according to the listed socioeconomic characteristics. Percentages above the threshold of 70% indicate a good match. The details, variable by variable, are reported in the Tables below.

Country	Match (%)
Germany	92.7%
Japan	90.2%
Poland	88.4%
UK	76.6%
Israel	71.6%
Italy	70.6%
USA	70.4%

Germany – 1'000 interviews	Population (EUROSTAT)	Realized Interviews	Weighting factors	Final Interviews
Gender	%	%		%
Male	49	48	1.0	49
Female	51	52	1.0	51
Age classes				
18-24	10	8	1.2	10
25-34	18	17	1.0	18
35-44	17	17	1.0	17
45-54	19	20	1.0	19
55-64	21	22	1.0	21
65-74	15	16	0.9	15
Occupation				
Employed persons	77	70	1.1	77
Unemployed persons	3	3	0.8	3
Persons outside the labour force	21	26	0.8	21
Education				
Up to lower secondary education (levels 0-2)	15	34	0.4	15
Upper and post secondary, non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4)	54	39	1.4	54
Tertiary education (levels 5-8)	31	27	1.1	31
Monthly income (household)				
up to EUR 1249	16	15	1.0	16
from EUR 1250 to EUR 1999	20	21	1.0	20
from EUR 2000 to EUR 2499	13	14	0.9	13
from EUR 2500 to EUR 3499	19	20	1.0	19
from EUR 3500 to EUR 3999	7	8	0.9	7
from EUR 4000 to EUR 4999	10	11	0.9	10
EUR 5000 and more	14	10	1.3	14
Region				
Baden-Württemberg	13	13	1.0	13
Bayern	16	16	1.0	16
Berlin	5	5	1.0	5
Brandenburg	3	3	1.0	3
Bremen	1	1	0.8	1
Hamburg	2	3	0.9	2
Hessen	8	7	1.1	8
Mecklenburg-Vorpommern	2	2	1.0	2
Niedersachsen	10	8	1.2	10
Nordrhein-Westfalen	22	23	0.9	22
Rheinland-Pfalz	5	5	1.0	5
Saarland	1	1	1.0	1
Sachsen	5	5	1.0	5
Sachsen-Anhalt	3	3	1.0	3
Schleswig-Holstein	4	4	1.0	4
Thüringen	3	3	1.0	3

Japan – 1'000 interviews	Population (MIC)	Realized Interviews	Weighting factors	Final Interviews
Gender	%	%		%
Male	49	52	0.9	49
Female	51	48	1.1	51
Age classes				
18-24	9	9	1.1	9
25-34	14	15	0.9	14
35-44	16	17	0.9	16
45-54	21	23	0.9	21
55-64	17	19	0.9	17
65-75	23	18	1.3	23
Occupation				
Employed persons	63	63	1.0	63
Unemployed persons	14	16	0.8	14
Persons outside the labour force	23	21	1.1	23
Education				
Up to lower secondary education (levels 0-2)	7	7	1.0	7
Upper and post secondary, non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4)	55	47	1.2	55
Tertiary education (levels 5-8)	38	46	0.8	38
Annual net income (household)				
less than 2m JPY	19	16	1.2	19
from 2m to 2,99m JPY	14	13	1.0	14
from 3m to 3,99m JPY	13	14	0.9	13
from 4m to 4,99m JPY	11	11	1.0	11
from 5m to 7,99m JPY	23	24	1.0	23
from 8m to 13,99m JPY	17	17	1.0	17
14m JPY and more	4	5	0.9	4
Region				
Hokkaido	4	5	0.9	4
Tohoku	7	7	1.0	7
Kanto	35	35	1.0	35
Chubu	17	17	1.0	17
Kansai	18	17	1.0	18
Chugoku	9	8	1.0	9
Kyushu	10	10	1.0	10
Okinawa	1	1	1.6	1

Poland – 1'000 interviews	Population (EUROSTAT)	Realized Interviews	Weighting factors	Final Interviews
Gender	%	%		%
Male	48	45	1.1	48
Female	52	55	0.9	52
Age classes				
18-24	10	10	0.9	10
25-34	18	20	0.9	18
35-44	22	23	0.9	22
45-54	17	18	0.9	17
55-64	18	19	0.9	18
65-75	16	9	1.7	16
Occupation				
Employed persons	71	70	1.0	71
Unemployed persons	2	3	0.8	2
Persons outside the labour force	27	27	1.0	27
Education				
Up to lower secondary education (levels 0-2)	7	11	0.6	7
Upper and post secondary, non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4)	60	53	1.1	60
Tertiary education (levels 5-8)	33	36	0.9	33
Personal net monthly income				
less than 500 PLN	11	8	1.4	11
from 500 PLN to 1500 PLN	15	15	0.9	15
from 1501 PLN to 2000 PLN	22	21	1.1	22
from 2001 PLN to 3000 PLN	16	18	0.9	16
from 3001 PLN to 4000 PLN	11	12	0.9	11
from 4001 PLN to 6000 PLN	16	17	0.9	16
6001 PLN and more	10	10	0.9	10
Region				
Makroregion Południowy	21	22	0.9	21
Makroregion Północno-Zachodni	16	17	0.9	16
Makroregion Południowo-Zachodni	10	11	0.9	10
Makroregion Północny	15	15	1.0	15
Makroregion Centralny	10	7	1.4	10
Makroregion Wschodni	14	15	1.0	14
Makroregion Województwo Mazowieckie	14	13	1.1	14

United Kingdom – 1'000 interviews	Population (Office for National Statistics)	Realized Interviews	Weighting factors	Final Interviews
Gender	%	%		%
Male	50	45	1.1	50
Female	50	55	0.9	50
Age classes				
18-24	16	8	1.9	16
25-34	18	20	0.9	18
35-44	18	19	0.9	18
45-54	17	19	0.9	17
55-64	18	19	0.9	18
65-75	14	15	0.9	14
Occupation				
Employed persons	65	70	0.9	65
Unemployed persons	3	3	0.8	3
Persons outside the labour force	33	26	1.2	33
Education				
Up to lower secondary education (levels 0-2)	14	12	1.2	14
Upper and post secondary, non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4)	55	52	1.1	55
Tertiary education (levels 5-8)	31	37	0.8	31
Weekly household income				
up to 399 GBP	26	25	1.0	26
from 400 GBP to 599 GBP	19	21	0.9	19
from 600 GBP to 799 GBP	14	15	0.9	14
from 800 GBP to 999 GBP	11	12	0.9	11
from 1000 GBP to 1399 GBP	14	12	1.1	14
from 1400 GBP to 1799 GBP	7	6	1.1	7
1600 GBP and more	9	9	1.0	9
Region				
ENGLAND	84	87	1.0	84
WALES	5	4	1.3	5
SCOTLAND	8	7	1.1	8
NORTHERN IRELAND	3	2	1.4	3

Israel – 1'000 interviews	Population (Central Bureau of Statistics)	Realized Interviews	Weighting factors	Final Interviews
Gender	%	%		%
Male	49	54	0.9	49
Female	51	46	1.1	51
Age classes				
18-24	17	21	0.8	17
25-34	21	26	0.8	26
35-44	20	24	0.8	20
45-54	17	19	0.9	17
55-64	14	7	2.0	12
65-75	12	3	4.4	9
Occupation				
Employed persons	69	82	0.8	74
Unemployed persons	4	5	0.8	4
Persons outside the labour force	27	13	2.0	22
Education				
Up to lower secondary education (levels 0-2)	13	7	1.9	13
Upper and post secondary, non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4)	53	46	1.1	48
Tertiary education (levels 5-8)	35	47	0.7	40
Monthly net income (household)				
up to 8529 ILS	20	22	0.9	21
from 8530 ILS to 13801 ILS	20	24	0.8	22
from 13802 ILS to 18487 ILS	20	23	0.9	20
from 18488 ILS to 24409 ILS	20	18	1.1	20
from 24410 ILS to 37172 ILS	15	9	1.6	12
37173 ILS and more	5	2	2.2	5
Region				
Jerusalem District	12	12	1.0	12
Northern District	9	7	1.3	9
Haifa District	11	14	0.7	14
Central District	29	25	1.1	26
Tel Aviv District	20	23	0.8	23
Southern District	14	16	0.9	14
Judea and Samaria Area	6	2	2.9	3

Italy – 1'000 interviews	Population (EUROSTAT)	Realized Interviews	Weighting factors	Final Interviews
Gender	%	%		%
Male	48	48	1.0	48
Female	52	52	1.0	52
Age classes				
18-24	10	13	0.7	13
25-34	15	15	0.9	15
35-44	18	19	0.9	18
45-54	22	24	0.9	22
55-64	20	19	1.0	20
65-75	16	10	1.6	13
Occupation				
Employed persons	59	63	0.9	59
Unemployed persons	6	10	0.6	9
Persons outside the labour force	35	27	1.3	32
Education				
Up to lower secondary education (levels 0-2)	37	17	2.3	37
Upper and post secondary, non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4)	43	52	0.8	43
Tertiary education (levels 5-8)	20	32	0.6	20
Annual income (individual)				
up to EUR 9999	30	22	1.4	30
from EUR 10000 to EUR 14999	13	14	0.9	13
from EUR 15000 to EUR 25999	30	28	1.1	30
from EUR 26000 to EUR 54999	23	29	0.8	23
from EUR 55000 to EUR 74999	2	4	0.5	2
from EUR 75000 to EUR 119999	2	2	0.7	2
EUR 120000 and more	1	1	0.7	1
Region				
North-west	27	28	0.9	27
North-east	20	17	1.2	20
Centro	20	21	1.0	20
South	23	21	1.1	23
Islands	11	13	0.9	11

USA – 2'000 interviews	Population (us Census Bureau)	Realized Interviews	Weighting factors	Final Interviews
Gender	%	%		%
Male	49	34	1.4	45
Female	51	66	0.8	56
Age classes				
18-24	13	6	2.3	8
25-34	19	14	1.4	15
35-44	18	23	0.8	23
45-54	17	18	1.0	17
55-64	18	20	0.9	18
65-75	15	20	0.8	19
Occupation				
Employed persons	60	58	1.0	60
Unemployed persons	3	6	0.5	40
Persons outside the labour force	37	36	1.0	
Education				
Up to lower secondary education (levels 0-2)	12	3	3.5	7
Upper and post secondary, non-tertiary education (levels 3 and 4)	58	54	1.1	58
Tertiary education (levels 5-8)	30	43	0.7	35
Annual income (household)				
up to USD 24999	9	14	0.7	9
from USD 25000 to USD 34999	17	19	0.9	17
from USD 35000 to USD 49999	12	15	0.8	12
from USD 50000 to USD 74999	17	21	0.8	17
from USD 75000 to USD 99999	12	13	0.9	12
from USD 100000 to USD 149999	23	12	2.0	23
USD 150000 and more	10	5	1.9	10
Region				
Northeast	17	21	0.8	17
Midwest	21	24	0.9	24
South	38	41	0.9	38
West	24	14	1.7	21

ANNEX V - Details about CERN awareness

Table 15 shows the percentage of respondents who declared to be aware of CERN as compared to other international and local organizations in each country. Numbers are expressed in percentages. For instance, 84% of respondents in Germany heard about NASA, while 42% about CERN. In non-European nations, NASA is always first, followed by WHO and UNESCO. In general, CERN lies in the middle.

The Table also shows insights about the awareness of national organisations. In Germany, the Max-Planck Gesellschaft (71%) and Fraunhofer Gesellschaft zur Förderung der angewandten Forschung (60%) are very well known by respondents. The same is true for the Japanese spatial agency JAXA and the RIKEN organization in Japan.

Table 15. Percentage of respondents aware of the listed organisations

Germany		Italy		Poland		UK		France		Switzerland	
NASA	84	NASA	88	NASA	89	NASA	84	UNESCO	89	UNESCO	93
UNESCO	83	UNESCO	87	WHO	89	WHO	80	NASA	86	NASA	93
WHO	76	WHO	80	UNESCO	87	UNESCO	63	WHO	82	OMS	83
Max-Planck Ges.	71	FAO	74	FAO	45	UK Space Ag.	58	CNSR	77	CERN	79
Fraun. GeS. zur F.	60	CERN	58	IMF	44	IMF	50	FMI	68	ASE	48
DLR	50	CNR	57	CERN	42	CERN	45	CERN	47	EMPA	40
ESA	49	IMF	48	POLSA	40	ESA	44	ESA	36	FMI	39
CERN	42	ASI	34	ESA	39	RI	30	CEA	32	FAO	29
KIT	14	ESA	25	IFJ PAN	19	FAO	30	FAO	22	PSI	27
IMF	13	INAF	13	ITER	6	JAI	12	ESRF	4	CSCS	7
FAO	12	INFN	12	ESRF	4	ITER	8			ESRF	3
DESY	8	ITER	8			RAL	7				
ITER	7	ESRF	3			ESRF	6				
ESRF	5	Sincrotrone	3			CI	5				
Israel		USA		Japan							
NASA	50	NASA	83	NASA	87						
WHO	49	WHO	72	WHO	86						
UNESCO	39	UNESCO	37	JAXA	74						
FAO	30	FAO	33	UNESCO	57						
CERN	28	CERN	28	IMF	55						
IMF	23	IMF	25	RIKEN	50						
ESA	23	ESA	19	CERN	12						
HCTPA	22	LANL	16	JST	11						
ITER	13	ORNL	10	FAO	10						
SESAME	12	Fermilab	9	ESA	10						
ESRF	9	SLAC	8	JASRI	5						
		LBNL	8	ITER	5						
		ITER	7	KEK	4						
		NIF	5	ESRF	2						

Sources: Authors. Total sample (n=1000 in each country, n=2000 in USA); % values * Switzerland surveyed in 2019, ** France surveyed in 2018

Table 16. Percentage of respondents by source of information about of CERN

	Germany	Italy	Poland	UK	Israel	USA	Japan
You know CERN because of...							
<i>TV, internet and social media</i>	26	43	29	33	16	20	9
<i>Books, newspapers</i>	16	25	16	12	6	9	4
<i>Films/documentaries on CERN</i>	17	13	13	12	7	8	2
<i>During studies</i>	8	16	10	10	6	5	2
<i>Through a person</i>	9	14	7	9	6	7	2
<i>Because of current/past job</i>	3	2	1	2	3	2	1
<i>Joining events organized by CERN</i>	2	1	1	1	2	1	0
<i>Visit of CERN</i>	1	2	1	1	2	1	0
Not aware of CERN	58	42	58	55	72	72	88

Total sample (n=1000 in each country, n=2000 in USA); % values

Table 17. What comes to your mind first when you think of CERN? % of respondents *before* the exposure to the information material

Germany		Italy		Poland	
Particle accelerator	27	Research/Scientific Research/Laboratories	28	Nuclear research	18
Nuclear research	21	Nuclear research	20	Research/Scientific Research/Laboratories	16
Research/Scientific Research/Laboratories	15	Research about particles	12	Particle accelerator	16
Research about particles	10	Particle accelerator	10	Research about particles	10
Organization located in CH / near border	10	Important Institute / Famous / Serious	7	Important Institute / Famous / Serious	9
Important Institute / Famous / Serious	9	Organization located in CH / near border	5	Organization located in CH / near border	9
Development / Innovation	3	Development / Innovation	5	Development / Innovation	3
Physical research	3	Physical research	5	Possibility of a better future	2
Universe origin research/Big Bang theory	3	Possibility of a better future	3	Physical research	2
Possibility of a better future	2	World famous / international institute	2	Universe origin research/Big Bang theory	2
World famous / international institute	1	Universe origin research/Big Bang theory	1	World famous / international institute	1
European institution	0	European institution	0	European institution	1
Other	4	Other	3	Other	4
No answer	6	No answer	6	No answer	18
Uk		France		Switzerland	
Particle accelerator	30	Research/Scientific Research/Laboratories	34	Research/Scientific Research/Laboratories	27
Nuclear research	19	Nuclear research	32	Particle accelerator	18
Research/Scientific Research/Laboratories	10	Particle accelerator	8	Nuclear research	11
Research about particles	9	Important Institute / Famous / Serious	7	Organization located in CH / near border	8
Important Institute / Famous / Serious	8	Organization located in CH / near border	4	Universe origin research/Big Bang theory	6
Organization located in CH / near border	7	World famous / international institute	4	Research about particles	5
Development / Innovation	3	Possibility of a better future	3	Physical research	5
Universe origin research/Big Bang theory	3	Physical research	3	Development / Innovation	4
Possibility of a better future	2	Universe origin research/Big Bang theory	3	Possibility of a better future	3
Physical research	2	European institution	3	World famous / international institute	3
World famous / international institute	1	Development / Innovation	1	Important Institute / Famous / Serious	2
European institution	0	Research about particles	0	European institution	1
Other	5	Other		Other	7
No answer	9	No answer		No answer	21
Israel		US		Japan	
Particle accelerator	18	Particle accelerator	22	Nuclear research	19
Research/Scientific Research/Laboratories	15	Research/Scientific Research/Laboratories	15	Research about particles	13
Important Institute / Famous / Serious	13	Nuclear research	14	Particle accelerator	10
Nuclear research	10	Important Institute / Famous / Serious	11	Research/Scientific Research/Laboratories	9

Possibility of a better future	7	Research about particles	7	Important Institute / Famous / Serious	6
Research about particles	5	Possibility of a better future	6	World famous / international institute	4
Development / Innovation	3	Development / Innovation	4	Physical research	2
Universe origin research/Big Bang theory	3	Universe origin research/Big Bang theory	4	Organization located in CH / near border	1
Organization located in CH / near border	2	Organization located in CH / near border	3	Possibility of a better future	1
World famous / international institute	2	Physical research	3	Development / Innovation	1
Physical research	1	World famous / international institute	2	Universe origin research/Big Bang theory	1
European institution	0	European institution	1	European institution	0
Other	8	Other	9	Other	10
No answer	17	No answer	6	No answer	29

Sources: Authors. Total sample (n=1000 in each country, n=2000 in USA); % values * Switzerland surveyed in 2019, ** France surveyed in 2018

Table 18 - What do you like about CERN? % of respondents *after* the exposure to the information material.

Germany		Italy		Poland	
Research / Scientific Research	34	Research / Scientific Research	39	Development / Innovation	31
Development / Innovation	21	Development / Innovation	25	Research / Scientific Research	22
International collaboration	9	International collaboration	9	Research about the universe	13
Research about the universe	6	Possibility of a better future	6	International collaboration	7
Possibility of a better future	4	Important Institute / Famous / Serious	5	Medical research	6
Medical research	4	Research about the universe	4	Possibility of a better future	4
Particle accelerator	3	Medical research	3	Particle accelerator	3
Physical research	2	Particle accelerator	2	Physical research	3
All	18	All	8	All	11
Other	9	Other	7	Other	6
At least 1 positive comment	89	At least 1 positive comment	92	At least 1 positive comment	88
UK		France		Switzerland	
Research / Scientific Research	27	Research / Scientific Research	29	Research / Scientific Research	39
Development / Innovation	26	Medical research	18	Medical research	18
Possibility of a better future	10	Development / Innovation	14	Development / Innovation	16
International collaboration	9	Research about the origin of the universe	12	Research about the universe	11
Research about the universe	9	World famous / international institute	9	World famous / international institute	11
Medical research	6	Research on particle	5	Possibility of a better future	7
Particle accelerator	2	Important Institute / Famous / Serious	5	Nuclear research	3
Physical research	2	Possibility of a better future	3	Physical research	2
World famous	2	Physical research	2	Important Institute / Famous / Serious	1
All	13	All	5	All	8
Other	7	Other	13	Other	12
At least 1 positive comment	81	At least 1 positive comment	83	At least 1 positive comment	97
Israel		USA		Japan	
Development / Innovation	25	Development / Innovation	26	Research / Scientific Research	18
Research / Scientific Research	23	Research / Scientific Research	24	Development / Innovation	14
Possibility of a better future	8	Possibility of a better future	9	Research about the universe	7
Research about the universe	7	Research about the universe	7	Possibility of a better future	7
World famous / international institute	7	International collaboration	6	International collaboration	3
Medical research	3	Medical research	4	Particle accelerator	2
Particle accelerator	2	Particle accelerator	3	All	4
All	17	All	16	Other	13
Other	10	Other	9	At least 1 positive comment	62
At least 1 positive comment	84	At least 1 positive comment	90	At least 1 positive comment	62

Sources: Authors. Total sample (n=1000 in each country, n=2000 in USA); % values * Switzerland surveyed in 2019, ** France surveyed in 2018

Table 19. What do not like about CERN? % of respondents after the exposure to the information material.

Germany		Italy		Poland	
Excessive cost	5	Low Safety	4	Low Safety	4
Low Safety	4	Lack of communication/Lack of information	3	Excessive cost	3
Subject too complex/difficult	3	Nuclear	3	Subject too complex/difficult	2
Lack of communication/Lack of information	2	Excessive cost	2	Lack of communication/Lack of information	2
Unnecessary trials/research scientific that I do not agree with	2	Subject too complex/difficult	2	Unnecessary trials/research scientific that I do not agree with	2
Video	2	Unnecessary trials/research scientific that I do not agree with	2	Video	1
Nuclear	2	Video	1	Nuclear	1
All	2	All	0	All	1
Other	3	Other	6	Other	4
At least 1 negative comment	25	At least 1 negative comment	21	At least 1 negative comment	19
UK		France		Switzerland	
Excessive cost	7	Subject too complex/difficult	7	Low Safety	10
Subject too complex/difficult	6	Low Safety	7	Excessive cost	7
Low Safety	5	Lack of communication/Lack of information	5	Lack of communication/Lack of information	5
Lack of communication/Lack of information	4	Nuclear	4	Subject too complex/difficult	3
Nuclear	3	Excessive cost	4	Unnecessary trials	3
Video	2	Unnecessary trials/research scientific that I do not agree with	2	Nuclear	1
Unnecessary trials/research scientific that I do not agree with	2				
All	2	All	1	All	1
Other	5	Other	5	Other	10
At least 1 negative comment	44	At least 1 negative comment	31	At least 1 negative comment	50
Israel		USA		Japan	
Low Safety	7	Low Safety	5	Subject too complex/difficult	10
Unnecessary trials/research scientific that I do not agree with	4	Excessive cost	4	Excessive cost	2
Lack of communication/Lack of information	4	Lack of communication/Lack of information	4	Video	2
Excessive cost	3	Subject too complex/difficult	3	Lack of communication/Lack of information	2
Nuclear	2	Video	3	Unnecessary trials/research scientific that I do not agree with	1
Subject too complex/difficult	2	Unnecessary trials/research scientific that I do not agree with	2	Low Safety	1
Video	2	Nuclear	2	Nuclear	0
All	2	All	5	All	3
Other	8	Other	5	Other	4
At least 1 negative comment	33	At least 1 negative comment	30	At least 1 negative comment	25

Sources: Authors. Total sample (n=1000 in each country, n=2000 in USA); % values * Switzerland surveyed in 2019, ** France surveyed in 2018

ANNEX VI - WTP distributions

This Annex reports the frequencies of the stated WTP by respondents in each country. For CERN member states, the overall distribution is reported, as well as the distribution of the sub-sample of respondents receiving the information about the per-capita tax contribution already paid to CERN (yes info) and the sub-sample that did not (no info). The mean WTP is visualised.

Germany

Israel

Italy

Poland

UK

USA

JAPAN

